

A situated and projective multi-scalar approach for local-regional planning

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Abstract

Contemporary regionalisation of urban and rural areas intensifies uneven geographic development. To counteract this development the aim of this paper is to formulate a situated and projective multi-scalar methodological approach beyond the urban and rural conceptual divide that can be used in contemporary regional development processes. The paper has been developed based on a compilation of three theoretical frameworks, and on a study of a regional development process in Sweden. The study shows how this multi-scalar approach can be used to connect and articulate spatial relations from a local to a regional scale, make visible possible futures and stage critical negotiations.

Keywords

Regionalization,
Uneven
Development,
Urban-Rural
Planning, Land-use
Strategies

Introduction – Uneven and linear relations between urban and rural

The increased mobility in society, territorial expansion, and the extensive structural changes that the city and the countryside have undergone since the 19th century have in many ways reformulated the relationships between regional and urban centres and peripheries and between urban and rural areas (see for example Lefebvre, 1996; Sieverts, 2003; Farhat, 2020). Today, both cities and countrysides are plural and differentiated and transformed into an intertwined urban-rural, regionalized landscape (Björling & Fredriksson, 2018; Shucksmith, 2018; Scott et al., 2019; Heike Johansen et al., 2023).

Simultaneously, ongoing urbanization processes promote uneven geographical development both on a global, national, regional, and local level (World Inequality Lab, 2018; UN, 2019). Even countries like Sweden that used to have relatively equal societal development are today experiencing growing regional differences in income, education, health, labour markets and welfare systems between growing metropolitan areas and regions with decreasing population (Syssner, 2015; Enflo, 2016).

Furthermore, historical, and contemporary linear flows of resources between rural and urban areas intensifies uneven distribution of resources and uneven political recognition with

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a negative effect on environmental impact, resource use, welfare, and democracy (Diaz et al., 2018; Jazeel, 2018; UN, 2019; Brenner, 2019; Keil, 2020; Angelo & Wachsmuth, 2020). A linear flow of resources also tends to increase inter- and intra-regional differences between rural areas as locations for extraction and exploitation and urban areas as locations for agglomeration of resources, waste, skills, and decision mandate (Björling, 2016; Arboleda, 2020; Campbell, et al., 2017; McKinnon et al., 2017; Kaika et al., 2023). The Swedish government has identified that there is a risk for suboptimization of local and regional resources if urban and rural areas are seen as separate entities rather than as cohesive structures (SOU, 2017).

To achieve a more just regional development beyond an urban and rural divide, there is a need to question the urban domination and to re-imagine the fundamental structures behind uneven spatial development, exploitation, and unsustainable accumulation of resources on both a local and a regional scale. Otherwise, there is a risk that ongoing and future industrial and capitalistic interests in rural areas and new demands for land use will promote uneven spatial relationships between urban and rural areas and increase conflicts of interest (Marsden, 2013; Scott et al., 2019). For example, a transition to a circular, bio-based, and fossil-free economy has been described as a possibility for rural areas to play a more central role in societal development, since increased focus is directed towards natural resources, vacant land, and energy supplies in rural areas (SOU, 2017; UN, 2019; EU, 2020). However, it is not certain that a transition to a circular economy will question the hierarchical relationship between urban and rural or between society and nature (Tzaninis, 2020). Instead, it can create new and enhanced uneven regional relationships, with increased conflicts of interest between different land-use interests such as for example food and energy production, location of new giga-factories, infrastructure corridors and between agricultural production and the tourism industry (Joensuu et al., 2020; Davoudi & Brooks, 2021).

To handle these contemporary complex urban-rural relationships, integrated planning strategies based on a holistic perspective on regional development is required (EU, 2020). Several researchers have developed theoretical concepts highlighting the need to question the hierarchical relationship between urban and rural and to develop more multi-scalar approaches. However, there are few examples of how these theoretical perspectives can be used as tools in regional development and transition.

With this as a background, the aim of this paper is to formulate a multi-scalar methodological approach beyond the urban and rural conceptual divide that can be used in contemporary local-regional transition processes.

The paper is organized in seven parts. After this introduction, we present the methodological approach and introduce the theoretical framework of city-centred regionalization, the urban - rural conceptual divide, and landscape as a relational and productive concept. Next, we describe the planning process for the regional plan for Skaraborg

and then, the process is analysed and discussed. In the discussion, we outline the implications of an applied approach to regional planning beyond the urban - rural conceptual divide, followed by the final remarks that conclude the paper.

Methodological approach

The methodological approach to regional planning has been developed based on a compilation of three theoretical frameworks, on a design-based participation and on analysis of a regional development process of the Skaraborg region in Sweden.

The Skaraborg region was selected for several reasons. The region is today a federation of municipalities and a sub-regional administrative unit within the region of Västra Götaland (see figure 1). Due to a long historical development the Skaraborg region consist of a diverse regional landscape where historical power-relations between different centres still plays an important role for the dynamics and conflicts of the region today. The Skaraborg region was also selected because of the fact that municipal actors demonstrated an interest in applying new approaches to local-regional planning and expanding the complementarity of the municipalities and to formulate a narrative of a region of a different kind. Using the Skaraborg region as a case made it therefore possible to test and critically discuss local-regional development in Sweden. Thus, Skaraborg was selected as a case relevant for analysis and method development since the region's strategies deviate from the common regional planning strategies in Sweden. In 2020 the regional plan won the planning price of the Swedish association of Architects (Sveriges arkitekters planpris).

The study of the regional development process has had a participatory research-by design-approach (Dyrssen, 2010), including analysis of policy documents, interviews, and practical participation in the planning process of a strategic development plan for the municipal federation of Skaraborg (Skaraborg, 2015; Björling, 2016). The methodological framework has been developed in an iterative process, where theory and practice has been developed in an integrated process. Design-based participation in the actual planning process has been used as a methodological 'prism' through which theoretical frameworks have been refracted and nuanced (von Busch, 2008, p.30). Vice versa, the findings of the empirical work have been elaborated and articulated based on the theoretical frameworks of Planetary Urbanization, Urban Political Ecology, and Landscape Urbanism.

Two guiding questions for the design-based process and analysis has been: 1) how to connect actors, resources, and decision mandate on several scales to establish a critique and resistance towards a neo-liberal planning paradigm and 2) how to project alternative futures beyond current spatial hierarchies and socio-economic dependencies.

The collaboration with the Skaraborg municipal federation has provided an opportunity to practically work and engage with an integrated process where the design and planning process has shifted between local, municipal, sub-regional and regional scales. The design-

based planning process has made it possible to combine articulation of alternative futures with critical and theoretical analysis. Projections of possible alternatives and discussions with civil servants and politicians have been used to identify relevant themes for the mapping the design process.

Based on the design-based participation in the planning process and the analysis of the development process, a multi-scalar approach that can be used in concrete planning processes has been formulated. Here, the focus has been to develop the analysis of the empirical material into a methodological approach that can be used in other local-regional planning processes.

A theoretical framework for the regionalised urban-rural landscape

Several researchers are highlighting an increasing regionalisation and a transformed political, social, and functional role of the region (see for example Mitander et al., 2013; Keil et al., 2016; Jonas & Moisiu, 2018 Davoudi & Brooks, 2021). The concept of regionalisation has several meanings, describing both distribution of decision mandate and responsibilities from transnational and national level to a regional level, as well as the transmission of power from local and municipal level to the regional level (Zonnerveld et al., 2012; Keil et al., 2016; ESPON, 2018). Furthermore, it refers to the increased regionalization of local labour markets and infrastructure systems as well as the regionalization of people's everyday lives, enforced by the increased mobility in society.

This section introduces a theoretical framework for the regionalised urban-rural landscape, starting out from the city-centric domination within contemporary planning discourse, and thereafter presenting an alternative approach to the regionalized landscape.

City-centred approaches to urban-rural development

Even though urban and rural areas today are transformed into an intertwined regionalized landscape, cities and metropolitan areas have a dominant role as fields of research, investments, and political interest (see for example Brenner & Schmid, 2014; Angelo & Wachsmuth, 2020; Tzaninis, 2020). The city-centric domination is widespread within academic, political, and journalistic discourse and several economical and sociological models have emphasised the strategical role cities play for financial flows and concentration of human capital (Jacobs, 1961; Krugman, 1991; 2011; Florida, 2002; 2017; Glaeser, 2011; Katz & Bradley, 2013).

However, several researchers have also emphasised the uneven effects of urbanization in the post-industrial era (Harvey, 2004; 2014; McKinnon, 2017; Robinson & Roy, 2016; Tzaninis, 2020; Angelo & Wachsmuth, 2020). This is not only an issue of economic dominance, but also a cultural one, where the idea of the city as ideal for the societal development stigmatizes other places and places them in a peripheral position (Robinson, 2013). This has primarily in a Scandinavian context been described as an *Urban norm* or

Urban Privilege (see for example Fredriksson, 2014; Rönnblom, 2017). Furthermore, researchers emphasize the need to fundamentally question economic models based on cities as places for realisation of capital in order to address a more sustainable and resilient rural-urban metabolism of resources (Marsden, 2013; Harvey, 2014; Walker & Moore, 2019; Kaika et al., 2023).

In the ongoing academic debate, several researchers have highlighted the increased interest in the countryside for the location of new giga factories, physical and digital infrastructure, new markets for fossil-free resources such as food, materials, and energy production in bio-based and circular economic models, as well as an increased interest in rural areas as places for tourism and recreation (Woods, 2012; Horlings & Marsden, 2014; Shucksmith, 2018; Heike Johansen et al., 2023). Rural areas are today characterized by structural transformation processes, from earlier being dominated by a few economic sectors within primarily food production, energy, and production of areal industries, to the contemporary situation where rural areas are influenced by several different functions such as for example bio-tech industries, data centres, battery-cell factories, tourism, and recreation (see for example Scott et al., 2019).

Beyond a binary conceptualization of the urban and rural

To question the hierarchical relationships between urban and rural areas, a critical spatial perspective on contemporary spatial transformations is needed. Several concepts with focus on bridging the traditional urban-rural divide have been developed during the last decades, such as *Postmetropolis* (Soja, 2000), *Zwischenstadt* (Sieverts, 2003), *Kulturlandschaft* (Christiansee & Wagner, 2014) *rurban* (Lefebvre, 1996; Björling, 2023; Björling & Rönnblom, 2023) *peri-urban*, *urban fringes*, *exourban* (Gallent et al., 2009; Qviström, 2013) and *post-productive landscape* (Scott et al., 2019). Furthermore Tzaninis et al. (2020) argue for a “more-than-urban” perspective, a statement in line with a similar critique that could be formulated as a more than rural perspective. These concepts broaden the understanding of the contemporary everyday regional landscapes that can neither be described as urban or rural, but rather as intertwined urban-rural hybrid conditions in its own right (McKinnon, 2017; Björling 2023).

An influential approach that can be used to describe the holistic influence of urbanization and the dynamics between multiple scales of the regionalized urban-rural landscape is the conceptual framework of *Planetary Urbanization*. This theoretical framework is based on the seminal work of Henri Lefebvre (2003 (1970)) and during the last decade developed by several researchers (see for example Brenner, 2013; 2019; Schmid et al., 2018; Robinson, 2013; and Wachsmuth, 2014). On the bases of the concept of Planetary Urbanization, Neil Brenner (2013) questions the understanding of urbanization as one process of migration from rural to urban areas. Brenner highlights (2019, p. 14) that the city is only one element of the

continuously changing geographies of capitalist agglomeration and extraction of resources, and that other territories, landscapes and ecologies are also operationalized, industrialized, capitalized, and transformed through urbanization processes. The urban, the rural and the regional are thereby not possible to define as specific scales, but should rather be understood as economic, institutional, political, cultural, and ecological configurations, as well as “vibrant forcefields of socio-spatial practices” inscribed in many different scales (Brenner, 2019, p. 3).

Planetary urbanization articulates the planetary scale of contemporary urbanization processes with both concentrating and extending logics that create an uneven urbanized landscape. According to Brenner (2019, p. 232), progressive planning therefore needs to explore new alternatives for urban transformations beyond contemporary processes based on competition between city-regions and city-centric neo-liberalizing. In this way a more just distribution of goods and resources, institutions and infrastructure in all spatial scales can be promoted.

The conceptual urban and rural divide and nature and society divide is further questioned by the theoretical framework of *Urban Political Ecology* (see for example Heynen et al., 2006; Ernstson & Swyngedouw, 2019; Walker and Moore, 2019; Kaika et al., 2023). This is further emphasised by Ray Patel and Moore (2018, p. 202), who are highlighting the uneven global distribution of resources and uneven geographic development on an institutional and systemic level. Patel and Moore (2018, pp. 202-212) problematize the abstraction of resources in monetary systems and emphasize the need to redistribute money and nonmonetary resources in order to repair the damages, hierarchies, and pervasive exploitation caused by historical and contemporary linear flows of resources and by the division between society and nature.

To challenge the linear flows of resources and the hierarchical relationship between binary concepts such as the society and the nature and the city and the country, Patel and Moore (2018, p. 206) argue for a combined process of resistance against ongoing transformation and formulation of alternative futures. This approach can be used in planning practice and research to critically discuss the spatial transformations of both urban and rural areas and to understand the role of urban and rural areas as intertwined places for production, reproduction, and consumption.

A critical and holistic approach to the regionalized landscape

To explore alternative spatial transformations of the urbanized urban-rural landscape, and to articulate spatial resistance against ongoing neoliberal transformation processes, several researchers and practitioners have highlighted the potential of using the concept of landscape as a framework to combine knowledge on urban, rural, and regional planning with knowledge on natural resources, agricultural production, and ecology. For example, the concept of landscape has been used within the theoretical framework of *Landscape Urbanism* to emphasise the dynamic relationships between society and nature within the field of built

environment and to highlight the spatial production of socio-ecological processes on a regional level (see for example Corner, 1999; 2006; Mostafavi & Doherty, 2010; Cuff & Sherman, 2011; Reed & Lister, 2014; Waldheim, 2016; Vicenzotti, 2018).

The concept of landscape has also been used in planning research to bridge the historical divide between urban and rural based on economic, social, and cultural factors, and to highlight ongoing conflicts of aesthetic, economic, socio-cultural and ecological interests between urban and rural logics for production and consumption (see for example McHarg, 1992 (1967); Cosgrove, 1998 (1984); Gallent et al. 2009; Qviström et al., 2019).

These theoretical perspectives articulate a productive and relational perspective on space and on the physical landscape, where material and discursive configurations enable possibilities for societal change and where spatial processes produce the conditions for the physical form of the landscape and for the spatial sense-making (Björling, 2016). Based on a relational perspective on landscape, Denis Cosgrove (2004) emphasizes that the landscape is a result of political struggles over land use, access to natural resources and to infrastructure. In line with Cosgrove, Charles Waldheim (2016) argues that the concept of landscape can be used as an active mediator within planning both to clarify conflicts and interactions between societal processes of change. Furthermore, Dana Cuff and Roger Sherman (2011, p. 30) highlight that the physical landscape can be seen as a platform where different interests are made visible and where urban design can stage critical negotiations about future spatial transformations.

Chris Reed and Nina-Marie Lister (2014) argue that this perspective on landscape emphasizes both the systemic conditions for societal transformation, and the projective ability where new design proposals, plans or strategic documents can change the narrative, the value, and the potential of the existing landscapes. This way of using the concept of landscape is a critique of the tendency to view landscape as a passive background to urbanisation (Corner, 1999; Waldheim, 2016; Qviström, 2017). Instead, landscape emerges as a situated multi-scalar concept that can connect spatial relations between urban and rural, and between the local and the regional scale (Waldheim, 2016), and that can project and make visible alternative futures to stage critical negotiations about exploitation and land-use (Cuff & Sherman, 2011; Patel & Moore, 2018)).

By combing the theoretical frameworks of Planetary Urbanisation, Urban Political Ecology and Landscape urbanism, a theoretical approach that bridges between urban and rural, questions the city centric approach to local-regional development, and emphasises the productive aspect of landscape is advocated. When formulating this into a methodological approach, it both addresses the need, and makes possible to: a) emphasize the intertwined urban-rural processes of concentrating and extending urbanization; b) articulate opposition to a city-centric and capitalistic local-regional development paradigm and understanding of local-regional resources; and c) make use of the productive capacity of landscapes to showcase

the potential for alternative spatial configurations that can open up for new narratives and political negotiations.

The planning process in the Skaraborg region

Context - The region of Skaraborg

The described theoretical framework has been tested and elaborated in the planning process in the Skaraborg region. The Skaraborg region is an administrative federation of 15 municipalities and has a total of 260 000 inhabitants and is since 1998 part of Region Västra Götaland, that has a total of 1 710 000 inhabitants. Geographically, it is located in the eastern part of Region Västra Götaland, between the two major lakes in Sweden, while Gothenburg, which is the largest city in Region Västra Götaland with 600 000 inhabitants is located in the western part (see figure 1). The Skaraborg region is today to a large extent one functional region but has during the last decades struggled with the division between its eastern and its western parts. 25% of the population commute to another municipality for work and 35% of the students in upper secondary school studies in another municipality than where they live (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015).

Figure 1: The Region Västra Götaland consists of four federations of municipalities: Fyrbodalen, Göteborg, Borås and Skaraborg.

Process - A common strategic development plan

In 2013 the municipalities in the Skaraborg region started a collaborative project with the aim to develop common strategies for sustainable growth, with focus on both meeting environmental goals, increasing equality and strengthening financial assets (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015). A project group with representatives from the municipalities of Skaraborg was created and [the author] was assigned as the project leader.

The planning initiative for Skaraborg was initiated by civil servants in Mariestad municipality in 2013. Mariestad Municipality is the former capital of the County of Skaraborg that were subsumed in the regional reorganisation of Region Västra Götaland in 1998. Increasing commuting to other municipalities, struggles to keep industry in Sweden and

ambitions to find ways to increase accessibilities to Mariestad through improvements in neighbouring municipalities was the arguments presented for creating a common strategic plan for the development of the Skaraborg region (Björling, 2016). Financing from the state (Tillväxtverket) made it possible to start a pilot project for a common strategic planning process.

In the initial phase of the project, major challenges were identified by the project group in collaboration with civil servants from the 15 municipalities. (See figure 2). Firstly, the metropolitan and city-centric understanding of a sustainable and successful regional development was identified as a challenge and the need to take advantage of the specific conditions for the region was highlighted. Secondly, the uneven geographic development that continuously relocates resources and population was identified as a challenge. Thirdly, the division between the different parts of the Skaraborg region was identified as a challenge creating inter-municipal competition as well as mental and physical barriers. Fourthly, the intermunicipal competition, leading to competition rather than collaborations between the municipalities in the region was emphasised as a challenge (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015, pp. 4-5, 17-19).

CHALLENGES

A REGION OF A DIFFERENT KIND

Skaraborg is a region of a different kind than for example, the Gothenburg region. The planning both within the Västra Götaland region and Skaraborg must get better to take advantage of Skaraborg's specific conditions and resources for regional development.

URBANIZATION

Concentrating and extending urbanization processes lead to relocation of population and resources.

DIVISION

A divided labor market needs combined in new ways to offer career paths and job opportunities for all. Physical and imagined barriers delimits within Skaraborg and to others parts of Sweden. (Illustrated here with Skaraborg daily newspapers)

COMPETITION

Comprehensive plans and visions leads to the municipalities trying to "Bid over each other". For growth in all of Skaraborg all municipalities need to get conditions to develop their specific resources.

Figure 2: Challenges Identified in the planning process of the strategic development plan for Skaraborg (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015).

After the challenges were identified in a collaboration between researchers and civil servants in three workshops and communicated to the political board, the project group conducted a qualitative mapping of different articulations of the region and its geography based on a review of historical maps and written reports (see figure 3). A historical mapping made visible how the development of the region was dependent both on the overall structural qualities of the regional landscape and on very detailed conditions in the landscape (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015). For example, most of the major squares in the towns

are located in the crossroads of the historical road-network, and the historical road-network and waterways establishes a topological hierarchy in the landscape. When the current road infrastructure was built, these locations and spatial hierarchies between the municipalities changed, both on a local and on a regional scale. For example, the prior topological position that Gothenburg has in the region has been enforced over time and the crossroad of regional roads are today often located outside the towns where new commercial centres that compete with the supply of service in the town centres has been established.

SKARABORG: historical layers – contemporary combinations

Figure 3: Historical layers of the landscape create contemporary combinations of resources (Björling, 2016)

Based on the mapping of historical shifts the project group together with representatives from the municipalities discussed possible future scenarios on an inter-municipal and intersectoral level. The process highlighted the dependencies between the different parts of the region and how the values of the landscape changed depending on focus.

To further analyse these relationships, the next step in the process entailed a detailed qualitative mapping of the current situation on regional and municipal level. The mapping was conducted by the project group in dialogue with municipal civil servants and civil servants at the Skaraborg federation of municipalities. In the mapping process, the dynamics of the region beyond its administrative territory were articulated, as well as how the regional context surrounding the municipalities changed depending on geographical position. For example, municipalities in the northern part of the region highlighted their need for good communication to areas north of the Skaraborg region. Similar issues were highlighted by the

municipalities in the southern part of the region, where regional administrative borders were not in line with the functional area of the local labour market, recreation areas, and the tourist areas.

When analysed in detail, the landscape of the northern part of Skaraborg revealed a topographical structure that historically has connected villages and countrysides along valleys and lake systems stretching from the north-western part of the Skaraborg region to south-eastern part of the region (see figure 4). This organisation of the landscape conflicts with the interest of increasing the connections to the areas north of Skaraborg. Changing scale in this part of the process articulated the region as a broader spectrum of different landscapes, infrastructures, and borders.

Figure 4: The detailed mapping of Tiveden between the lakes Vänern and Vättern identified how the landscape in detail constrain or enable connections and constitute physical and mental borders.

Based on the identified challenges and the inter-municipal mapping of the landscape, common principles and strategies for sustainable growth were developed together with representatives and politicians from the municipalities (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015). The aim of this part of the process was to raise a political debate and to define multiple landscapes and their interconnection (see figure 5). The project group highlighted the need to base the development of a common strategy on a plural and holistic perspective on regional development (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015).

Figure 5: The mapping process resulted in a strategic development plan where the regional landscape is seen as a common intermunicipal interest.

The result of the process described above was a strategic development plan for regional development in the Skaraborg region based on the understanding of Skaraborg as a coherent landscape with in total 260 000 inhabitants. This approach aimed to develop a more robust regional network where the Skaraborg region and all the municipalities in the region are interpreted as the centre of its own geographical context (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015).

Another result of the process was the establishment of an inter-municipal group of planners that today form an arena for an ongoing conversation and debate on how to continuously include these perspectives in the planning processes in all 15 municipalities in the Skaraborg region.

The strategic development plan was presented to the political board in February 2016 and has since then been used by the Skaraborg municipal federation to develop three common thematic comprehensive plans: *Business region Skaraborg* (Business region Skaraborg, 2022), *Regional road networks for tourism* (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2019a), and *Charge infrastructure for electric and bio-fuel vehicles* (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2019b).

The political ambitions in the Skaraborg region have during the last years been focused on how the Skaraborg region can make use of its accessibility to land, energy, and labour market within the automobile industry to promote industrial renewal. The municipalities in the region have in different constellations been part of large-scale investment promotions to attract new companies and investments, and in august 2022 Volvo trucks decided to invest in a giga-factory for batteries in Mariestad municipality – a situation that are currently boosting the political discussion about collaborations and multi-level governance.

Analysis - Renegotiating a regional landscape of a different kind

The challenges formulated in the first part of the development process (see figure 2) was the result of a dialogue between researchers and practitioners where the concepts of *Planetary Urbanisation* and *Urban Political Ecology* was applied in the common mapping and analysis of the challenges and potential of the built environment and landscape of the region of Skaraborg. The results of the design-based mapping process emphasised the need to formulate strategies for a combined urban-rural regional landscape, and to strengthen the local resources and the specific spatial qualities and relationships in the Skaraborg region. The process of formulating the strategic development plan for the Skaraborg region can thus be seen as a process that, through the application of theoretical concepts such as the concentration and extension of urbanization and urban metabolism, has opened up for an alternative narrative of the regional situation. It has also highlighted that the administrative organization of the municipalities in the Skaraborg region is, in many ways, detached from the geographical structure as well as the functional, everyday connections in the region.

The critique of a city-centred narrative of regional development based on economic growth in cities created at the same time intermunicipal tensions when different municipalities were asked to collaborate and agree on how to share common needs for investments and to prioritize where to invest. For example, the project group identified problems connected to commuting patterns, local labour markets, agricultural production and tourism bridging municipal and regional administrative borders. These challenges also created a discussion between civil servants and politicians about what to describe as centres and peripheries in the region depending on perspective. This showcases how the design-based process was used to transform the critique of the city-centric perspective formulated within planetary urbanization, as well as the need to re-evaluate the views on urban and rural, centre and periphery, and on production and reproduction highlighted within Urban Political Ecology, into concrete methodological planning tools.

In the next part of the process where the focus turned towards the historical layers and multi-scalar logic, the historical rescaling of centres and peripheries was brought up for political discussion, both in relation to how new regional infrastructure strengthens the larger cities as regional nodes, and in relation to how new infrastructural nodes outside the town

centres creates new nodes detached from the topological and historical system. For example, “external” shopping areas in the larger cities in the Skaraborg region was highlighted to rather be seen as “internal” interregional nodes that changes the preconditions for service in the surrounding municipalities and creates new economic connections between the different municipalities and between the cities and the countrysides. The historical perspectives on the landscape also showed how current centres and peripheries are a result of negotiations and territorial struggles that have changed over time and probably will continue to change in the future.

Furthermore, the articulation of the region of Skaraborg as a common landscape and how specific spatial interventions in one place enable and constrain possibilities for development, not only in the local context but also in the region as a whole, opened up for intermunicipal negotiations about land-use and possible common public investments in the Skaraborg region. For example, it generated a discussion between the municipalities about how Skaraborg can attract new industrial businesses by combining service in the towns with attractive housing close to the water and how the municipalities can share welfare distribution between municipalities in the smaller towns (Business region Skaraborg, 2022).

In a similar way, the mapping of the differences in municipal perspectives on the development in the region showcased how different parts of the region is articulated in different ways depending on the point of departure. For example, the in-between landscape of the countrysides was articulated as a common intermunicipal interest when the focus in the mapping process were shifted from the regional to the local and back to the regional scale again. Furthermore, the thematic mapping of for example housing, labour market, education, agricultural production, and natural reserves, highlighted how the common landscape could be interpreted in different ways depending on perspective. This iteration between mapping territorial landscapes and thematic landscapes and analysing regional and local contexts helped the civil servants and later the politicians to change perspectives from a competitive perspective to seeing more mutual benefits of cooperation (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015).

The multi-scalar approach used by the project group made it possible to re-evaluate and highlight the relationship between socio-ecological consumption and the landscape where the resources are produced, such as how the use of concrete and timber in buildings and infrastructure transforms the surrounding landscape by creating stone quarries and clear-felling of the forest, or how a dry season for the agricultural sector results in a shortage of barley and wheat. Furthermore, the project group used the mapping to show how the provision of welfare systems for healthcare and education was distributed between the municipalities and how the regional landscape of economic production and social re-production was creating geographical hierarchies between socio-economic centres and peripheries (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015).

By emphasising the consequences of current spatial hierarchies and uneven geographic development in the region, and by challenging a city-centric approach, other alternatives were possible to articulate and project. For example, the project group focused on how resources could be valued from a holistic perspective of regional production, how regional identities could be developed beyond urban or rural stereotypes and how centre and periphery in the region could be reinterpreted (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015).

Step by step, the developed strategies became focused on articulating new combinations of resources from the whole regional landscape, to challenge Gothenburg as the main city and “core” of the Region Västra Götaland (VGR, 2013), to challenge Skövde as the main city and core in the Skaraborg region and to challenge the central towns as prioritized for municipal development (Björling, 2016). Thus, the city-centred planning process was challenged both on a regional, sub-regional and municipal level.

The results of the planning process implied a shift from a regional development strategy mainly focused on the metropolitan areas and infrastructural corridors, to a regional development also highlighting the villages, the agricultural landscape, the lakes, and the forests.

This attempt to shift focus from a city-centric to a more holistic approach on the regional landscape was also based on the idea of a shift to a more circular economy. Due to its geological and topographical conditions, the Skaraborg region is rich in ecosystem-based resources like clean water, food production and biodiversity. However, the project group also saw a risk that a shift to a circular economy could create new uneven regional relationships, with increased conflicts of interest between different land-use interests such as food and energy production and between agricultural production and the tourism and recreation industry. Therefore, the municipalities in the Skaraborg region saw a need to keep a critical and pluralistic perspective on spatial change and to continuously open for negotiation about different alternatives (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015).

The regional landscape in the Skaraborg Region is today still a field for political negotiation but is considered more as a common interest where applied strategies challenge a city-centric understanding of the Västra Götaland region. Based on a more holistic perspective on the region, all fifteen municipalities are made visible as hybrids of several productive landscapes and infrastructural layers that can contribute to the common development in different ways.

A multi-scalar approach to local-regional planning

Based on the compilation of the theoretical framework and the elaboration through the design-based study of the Skaraborg region we argue that a city-centric approach to regional planning can be challenged by approaches that combine holistic, critical, situated, and projective perspectives. The development process in Skaraborg where this approach has been developed

and tested can be described in four steps. Even if the process is described in clear steps that follows each other, it is important to highlight that the approach has required continuous feedback loops between involved actors and planning levels. Furthermore, it has required an openness between formulation, evaluation, and reformulation of problem statements and local-regional imaginaries. The methodological approach can be operationalized through the following steps:

1) *A tentative goal was formulated, and questions initial questions were clarified.* This was not intended to simplify the problem but was rather a first step to situate the process in order to outline a relevant and often complex context. This meant that the process started with the overall purpose to "create growth in the whole region of Skaraborg". This goal was based on both the limitations created by an uneven development in the Skaraborg region, and on the political ambitions to strengthen the competitiveness of the region and to reduce vulnerability resulting from for example an aging population and a lack of competences for the businesses in the region.

2) *A mapping process of territorial and thematic landscapes such as topography, topology, resources, potentials, and processes were initiated.* This included several mapping processes in dialogue with local planners and actors, from mapping of the geological processes that shaped the Skaraborg region, historical processes, and changes in power relations between different locations, to contemporary commuting patterns and thematic mapping of resources of the different parts of the region. These mappings have subsequently formed a common knowledge base that can be used to identify power relations, and to identify possible transformations of the built environment.

3) *Possible combinations of resources that are made visible when viewing places as centres of their own context were examined.* In for example the area of Tiveden, the lack of public transport was seen as a problem. When Tiveden was placed in the center of its own context, the mapping showed that the border area has a topography which historically has created strong connections within the area located between the two larger lakes Vänern and Vättern, which today creates strong local networks between businesses and associations. On the other hand, the topography limits the accessibility in the north-south direction. The landscape could in this way be used as a lens to articulate the constrains and project new combinations of regional and local collaborations and re-value resources and processes that were obscured by the existing condition.

4) *The projective landscape was used as material and discursive platforms for negotiation.* By modelling Skaraborg as a network of interconnected urban and rural areas, alternative future landscapes that made visible conflict of interests emerged. This made it possible for politicians, civil servants from regional and municipal level and private investors to see the opportunities and limitations that different imaginaries created. The idea of the "network city" articulated a possibility for negotiations about where to focus and distribute

future investments, and for political discussion about who benefits and who loses from different options.

Discussion – Articulating alternatives and plural perspectives

Contemporary city-centric regionalization in Sweden, as well as in many other European countries, is on the one hand side characterized by a dissolvment of historical boundaries between urban and rural, whilst on the other hand by increasing differences in living conditions between new centres and peripheries, both on a regional and on a municipal level. These spatial differences are reinforced by the fact that urban prerogatives have been dominating and are still dominating the planning practice and policy making during the expansion of the Swedish welfare state.

To achieve a more just regional development beyond a city-centric perspective, an approach that goes beyond the urban - rural conceptual divide is needed. In this paper, a holistic, critical, and situated approach to urban-rural landscapes has been elaborated and analysed. This has been done by a design-based research process applied in a regional development process in the Skaraborg region.

The approach developed for the regional plan in the Skaraborg region has been influential in the regional and national discourse on local-regional planning processes in Sweden in recent years. The developed approach highlighted the problems with uneven regional development and the constrains that follows when certain parts of the region lack capacity to handle future transformation of the physical landscape. When the plan won the Swedish planning price in 2020 the jury highlighted that the regional plan for Skaraborg questions norms and tackles complex issues in a serious and critical way by giving the city and the countryside equally important roles to play, and by moving from competition between municipalities to stronger cooperation. By approaching regional development from an expanded concept of growth, the jury emphasised that the process has given social, cultural, and ecological values greater impact and has promoted a process that enables a more just geographical development. (www.arkitekt.se).

The projective approach developed in this paper enabled a critical dialogue that highlighted a plurality of future alternatives and made it possible to challenge business as usual in the Skaraborg case. It shows how a holistic, critical, situated, and projective, multi-scalar methodological approach can be used to highlight conflicts of interest regarding, for example, land use, extraction, and distribution of resources. Furthermore, the process in which theory and practice have been combined to develop new transdisciplinary knowledge showcases how academic knowledge can be transferred and further elaborated in planning practice. In the Skaraborg development process, the shifting between scales has made it possible to articulate both the overall systemic impact and the spatial details of specific strategies. This approach has made it possible to expand political visions and negotiate how

political discourses and decisions become materialized in the regionalized urban-rural landscape. The case of the Skaraborg region thereby shows how a design-based approach can challenge a city-centered approach to regional planning and formulate a multi-scalar approach beyond the urban-rural divide.

This multi-scalar approach to regional planning emphasises the spatial dimensions of planning and the importance of clarifying the functions, possibilities, and limitations that different configurations of landscapes create based on topography, natural and cultural environment, land use, infrastructure, buildings, administrative demarcations, and regional imaginaries. The landscape is in this way not seen as passive backdrop to regional planning, but rather as continually assembled of several different conditions and landscapes that both provide opportunities and limits how society and individuals can change their living environment over time.

Furthermore, this approach to regional planning can be used to bridge the gap between abstract models of circular economy and the concrete spatial consequences that follow. As Gallent et al. (2009) highlight, planning and design of the physical landscape can be used to steer the transition to a circular and fossil-free economy in a more sustainable direction by enhancing the regenerative effects on socio-ecological systems, counteracting the unequal effects of exploitation, and limiting the impact on planetary systems and the distribution of resources. This addresses what Brenner (2019) describes as a multi-scalar, structural approach to handling both local and institutional needs. As the process in the Skaraborg region shows, it is, however, important to continuously keep the planning process open for renegotiation regarding the local-regional spatial impact of societal change and political decision in order not to fall back into a linear top-down planning process. Here, the holistic and projective multi-scalar approach can be used to continually make visible and stage political debate about, for example, changes in land use and investments in new infrastructure.

If the transformation to a circular economy is not combined with a critical perspective on which values are created locally in all parts of the circular loop, there is a risk that new unintended spatial hierarchies will be created. Therefore, the changes in the use of the physical landscape need to be combined with a critical discussion about where the economy is realized and reinvested in local development and landscape transformation. For example, the potential for a new and stronger role for the Skaraborg region as a landscape to establish circular flows of resources was used to re-evaluate local-regional resources in the Skaraborg region (Skaraborgs kommunalförbund, 2015). However, the project also recognized a risk for increased conflicts of interest between different land-use interests and identified a need to keep a critical perspective and remain continuously open to re-negotiation about different alternatives.

Final remark

We argue that a situated and projective multi-scalar approach to planning can be used as a tool to bridge administrative and disciplinary borders, to work beyond the traditional dichotomies of urban and rural, and to identify new productive and relational landscapes and spatial conflicts beyond conceptual divides. The situated and projective aspect of landscape and the built environment can here be used to coordinate interests and perspectives and stage critical negotiations about land-use, regulation, and balance of private and public interests, as well as to evaluate the societal consequences of multi-scalar spatial struggles and to articulate new political alternatives beyond an urban-rural divide.

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Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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